

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers:

Summer is certainly still noticeable in J.UCS. Although we have many papers in the refereeing process most editors seem to currently relax somewhere on a beach, mountain or whatever, so reports are coming in rather sluggishly: the August issue consists of only two papers, this time!

Thus, although I naturally want to encourage everyone to continue submitting high-quality papers, my particular plea today goes to all the editors to (i) take on more papers for refereeing than most are currently doing and (ii) try to complete the refereeing job as fast as possible.

To contributors I apologize for delays that may have occurred, but hope that "refereeing discipline" is going to improve again in fall.

Happy reading!

All the best,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer
email: hmaurer@iicm.tu-graz.ac.at